

Checking and correcting the setup error of rotating phantom in pre-treatment verification of VMAT radiotherapy plans

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Abstract Purpose: To check the setup position of the Octavius phantom in pre-treatment verification of VMAT radiotherapy plans and to reduce the influence of the setup error on gamma analysis.

Methods: The gamma index measures the difference between the computed dose distribution by the treatment planning system and the dose distribution obtained with the QA device in pre-treatment plan verification. The gamma index is affected by several factors. One of these is the rotating phantom setup position error. To estimate the later in complex dose distributions, instead of 'Align Automatically' function implemented in Verisoft program, our method is presented. We carry out the determination of the phantom shift before the treatment plan verification. It based on obtaining dose distributions an anterior-posterior and a lateral square field. The phantom's shift is obtained by comparing theirs position with orthogonal fields being in exact position. After performing the pre-treatment verification measurement of the actual RT plan, the 3D dose matrix generated by the Verisoft program is shifted to opposite directions with the obtained shifts. After them, the gamma analysis is performed. The phantom setup error correction method was tested with 10 head and neck simultan- integrated boost and additional boost and 10 prostate ones with boost.

Results Significant increase in gamma index was given after setup error correction especially when 2mm distance and 2% dose criteria was used, while we experienced low variation in gamma index with 3mm distance and 3% dose criteria.

Conclusion The presented method allows the user to check and correct the rotating phantom's setup error within 0.5-2mm range.

keywords: pre-treatment verification, rotating phantom setup

Introduction

At our institution, the pre-treatment verification of volumetric modulated arc (VMAT) radiotherapy plans (RTP) with the Octavius 4D phantom with 729 ion chamber array (PTW. GMBH, Freiburg, Germany) is performed. The verification of RTPs with the Verisoft program v6.2 (PTW) is based on the comparison of the two 3D dose distributions. The first one is obtained from the measured 2D dose matrices by the ion chamber array, while the second one is the dose matrix of the corresponding RT plan adapted for the geometry of the Octavius phantom by the Monaco v5.11 (Elekta BV., Sweden) treatment planning system (TPS). The comparison of the two dose matrices for spatial and dose difference is performed with gamma analysis. For definition and interpretation of the gamma index and gamma analysis see ref. [1]. The gamma index is affected by several factors analyzed by Urso et al.[2]. One of the factors is the phantom setup error. The Verisoft program offers the 'Align Automatically' function to correct the rotating phantom's setup error. This function works fine for simple dose distributions but often resulted in a poorer gamma index for complex dose distribution. The aim of the study was to develop an alternative method to estimate the rotating phantom's location error and to decrease the influence on the gamma index.

Materials and methods

Before the pre-treatment verification measurements are performed, the phantom is carefully positioned and leveled with the room lasers and the chamber array is cross-calibrated. Before the pre-treatment verification measurement, we determine the rotating phantom's setup position with an anterior-posterior (AP) and a lateral field (LAT) of 10x10 cm. 1Gy dose is delivered per fields to the Octavius phantom. The two fields' position is compared to the reference AP and LAT fields of 10x10cm with exact position. The later were generated with the planning system previously. The shifts of the phantom in lateral (L) and Gantry-Target (GT) direction are obtained with the AP field compared to the position of the AP reference field with the Verisoft program's 'Align Automatically' function. Similarly, comparing the lateral field's position with the lateral reference field, the phantom's vertical shift (S) is obtained. After performing the pre-treatment measurement of the RT plan and computing the 3D dose distribution by the Verisoft program, the corresponding shifts in opposite directions to the 3D dose matrix is applied and the gamma index is computed.

The method was tested with 40 RT plans, 10 head and neck RT plans with boost and 10 prostate plans with sequential boost illustrated in Fig.1.and 2. The two plan approach was used. The dose prescription for the head and neck plans was: 50 Gy to the lymph nodes and simultaneous boost of 10 Gy to the low risk and high risk target volume. After them, 10Gy boost to the high risk target volumes was administered. The dose prescription for the prostate plans was: 46 Gy to the lymph nodes and simultaneous boost of 14Gy to seminal vesical and prostate. After them, boost of 14 Gy to the prostate was administered with fractional dose of 2Gy. The RT plans were generated with Monaco v5.11 treatment planning system with 6MV energy and the Monte Carlo algorithm. The pre-treatment verification measurements were carried out with Synergy linear accelerator with Agility MLC (Elekta B.V.)

Fig.1-2. Coronal view of head and neck and prostate RT plan.

Gamma indexes of 3mm distance-to-agreement and 3% dose difference to reference, the maximal dose in volume (3/3 criteria) and gamma indexes of 2mm distance and 2% dose agreement (2/2 criteria) were computed. The corrected minus uncorrected gamma indexes of different RT plans and with the two criteria are illustrated in Fig.3.

Fig.3. Corrected minus uncorrected gamma indexes of different RT plans and with the 3/3 and the 2/2 criteria

The setup error (SH) of the Octavius phantom is defined as a square root of sum of squares of lateral, sagittal and gantry-target direction shifts varied between 0.4-2mm. In few cases, we experienced larger shift, identified with slippage of the detector array, there were excluded from the study. The number of RT plans with difference between the corrected minus uncorrected gamma indexes >1% and the p-values of paired t-test obtained with Microsoft Excel 2010 are summarized in Table 1.

Table1. The number of RT plans with difference in gamma index larger than >1% after phantoms shift correction and the corresponding p-values of paired t-test

Evaluation criteria	3/3	2/2	3/3	2/2
Head and Neck RT plans	1	6	0.009	0.0045
Head and Neck boosts	3	8	0.0045	0.005
Prostate RT plans	1	6	0.003	0.002
Prostate boost	3	8	0.0029	0.0015

Results

Our method in determination of the rotating phantom shift was found effective in submillimeter-millimeter range. After correcting the phantom setup error with shifting the dose matrices, we experienced significant (>1%) increase in gamma index in 60-80% of RT plans with 2/2 criteria, while the increase of gamma index was smaller in 10-30% of RTPs when 3/3 criteria was used. The correction was effective for larger than 0.5 mm phantom shifts, while little difference was shown in gamma index when the phantom's shift was small.

Conclusion

Instead of 'Align Automatically' function implemented in Verisoft program for attempting to correct position of complex dose distribution, we check the phantom's setup location prior to the QA measurement series. The method, summarized in Appendix, was found suitable to check whether the Octavius phantom is located in the right position

and was found suitable to determine the phantom's shift. The user also can correct small setup errors in millimeter and submillimeter range for the accurate gamma analysis. The corrections were effective for shifts larger than 0.5mm and with the 2/2 criteria.

Declaration of interest: none.

References

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Appendix

Summary of steps for checking and correction the Octavius phantom's position for the accurate gamma index evaluation.

Pre-requisites

Dose matrices of two reference fields' computed by the treatment planning system with the following parameters:

field size: 10x10cm, gantry angle: 0 degree and 90 degrees, the isocenter is located at the: Octavius phantom center

dose: 1Gy at the isocenter

Determination of the phantom's shift

1. Positioning and levelling the Octavius phantom with room lasers.
2. Calibration of the ion chamber array (air pressure and temperature correction).
3. Delivering the AP and lateral fields to the phantom with the same parameters as the reference fields.

4. Obtaining the lateral (L) and Gantry-Target direction (GT) shifts between the measured by the ion chamber array and reference fields with the Verisoft program's 'Align Automatically' function with the AP field.
5. Obtaining the sagittal shift with the lateral field (S).

QA check of RT treatment plans

- 1 Performing the QA measurements with RT treatment plans adapted to the rotational phantom
2. Performing the gamma index evaluation as usual way.
3. Correction the measured dose matrix's position by shifting with L, GT and S in opposite direction.
4. Repeating the gamma index evaluation.
5. Comparing the corrected and uncorrected gamma indexes.